

ЧАСТОТА І ПРЕДИКТОРИ ІМПЛАНТАЦІЇ ШТУЧНОГО ВОДІЯ РИТМУ (ШВР) ПІСЛЯ ПРОТЕЗУВАННЯ АОРТАЛЬНОГО КЛАПАНА

FREQUENCY AND PREDICTORS FOR PERMANENT PACEMAKER IMPLANTATION AFTER AORTIC VALVE REPLACEMENT

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The purpose of our study was to identify the frequency and predictors for permanent pacemaker implantation (PPI) in patients who have undergone isolated surgical aortic valve replacement under artificial blood circulation (ABC).

Materials and methods. Data from 1541 patients aged 18 to 80 years (62.1 ± 7.9 years) with isolated aortic valve replacement that was performed at the Heart Institute Ministry of Health of Ukraine from 01.2008 to 01.2021 were retrospectively analyzed. Indications for surgery were the following: aortic valve stenosis (n = 510/33,1%), insufficiency (n=256/16,6%), combination stenosis-insufficiency (n = 775/50,3%). The aortic bicuspid valve was present in 320/20.8% of cases, a re-operation was performed for 123/8% of patients.

The analyzed parameters were the following: age, sex, symptoms, type of valve anomaly, pathologies of the heart conduction system and heart rhythm, echocardiographic parameters, the presence and severity of valve calcification, ABC time, aortic compression time, type and diameter of valve prostheses, method of surgical implantation. Statistical evaluation of the compared data was performed by correlating the calculated value of the reliability criterion p with the threshold value of 0.05.

Results. In the early postoperative period (on average 30±12 days), 130 of 1541 patients required PPI which accounted for 3.55% of all cases. 6/4,6% of patients developed second-degree atrioventricular (AV) block, 124/95,4% of patients manifested complete AV block.

Patients with electrocardiographic signs of pre-operative heart conduction disorder required PPI significantly more often compared with patients with normal heart conduction (16% versus 6%, $p = 0.004$). It was found that patients with aortic insufficiency had a significantly higher need for PPI (16% versus 7%, $p = 0.01$).

Independent predictors of PPI were also: large pre-operative end-systolic diameter ($p = 0.026$), ventricular hypertrophy ($p = 0.04$), the degree of aortic valve calcification ($p = 0.001$).

A larger size of the aortic valve prosthesis correlated with significantly more frequent implantation ($24,8 \pm xx$ mm versus $27 \pm xx$ mm, $p = 0,02$). Independent predictors of PPI were the following: a big preoperative end-systolic diameter ($p = 0.026$), ventricular hypertrophy ($p = 0.04$), the degree of aortic valve calcification ($p = 0.001$).

Conclusions. The main risk factors for PPI are a diagnosed aortic valve insufficiency, the presence of pre-operative disorders of the heart conduction system, a bigger size of an artificial heart valve.